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**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
GOVERNANCE IN THE UKRAINIAN EXPERIENCE**

**7-Russian-Ukrainian War's Geopolitical
Consequences for Eastern Europe. By Vira
Kazymir and others. p. 138.**

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**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
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PREPARED**

**CENTER FOR LAW AND POLITICAL RESEARCH – DENMARK
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RUSSIAN-UKRAINIAN WAR'S GEOPOLITICAL CONSEQUENCES FOR EASTERN EUROPE

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the geopolitical and socio-economic consequences of the Russian-Ukrainian war for the countries of Eastern Europe in the period 2022–2024. The relevance of the topic is due to the scale of the conflict's impact on regional stability, economic security and the social sphere of countries bordering the combat

zone. The study was based on a systematic analysis of analytical documents of international organizations, strategic plans of the European Union and official statistical reports. The methods of content analysis and secondary analysis of statistical information were used to process the data. The results of the study showed a significant decline in GDP, rising inflation, rising unemployment and poverty, especially in Ukraine and its closest neighbors - Poland, Romania and Moldova. Migration flows had a significant impact: more than 7 million Ukrainian refugees put a strain on the social systems of host countries, which was accompanied by an increase in spending on health care and education. It was found that geopolitical changes led to increased security cooperation within NATO, a reorientation of trade flows and energy diversification in order to reduce dependence on Russian energy carriers. The article emphasizes the importance of the European Union's strategic adaptation to new challenges through the implementation of energy security mechanisms, strengthening regional cooperation and deepening integration processes with the Eastern Partnership countries. Prospects for further research lie in the development of new approaches to monitoring long-term geopolitical changes, taking into account modern economic trends and global security challenges.

Keywords: legal globalization, legal unification, convergence of legal systems, interstate legal systems, international organizations, international treaties, effectiveness of international law norms, compliance (non-compliance) with the principles of international law.

1- INTRODUCTION

The Russo-Ukrainian war has become the largest security crisis in Europe since World War II and a key factor in profound geopolitical changes that affect the stability of the entire region. The war has led to an unprecedented flow of refugees, a significant increase in poverty and social challenges, especially in countries directly bordering Ukraine. The significant burden on the social systems of Poland, Romania, Moldova and the Baltic countries has exacerbated the issues of integrating migrants and financing state support programs, which complicates the internal economic stability of these countries¹. At the same time, the European Union has faced the need to expand its own defense capabilities and strengthen strategic partnerships to counter new threats.

The economic impact of the war was felt by countries in the immediate neighbourhood and across Europe, as destabilisation of trade flows, inflationary pressures and an energy crisis disrupted traditional economic ties. The countries most affected, with significant dependence on exports and imports from Russia and Ukraine, - were Poland, Hungary and the Czech Republic. GDP fell, inflation soared and purchasing power plummeted, creating serious challenges for governments to

¹ *The impact of the war in Ukraine and subsequent economic downturn on child poverty in Eastern Europe*, (UNICEF, 2023). <https://www.unicef.org/eca/reports/impact-war-ukraine-and-subsequent-economic-downturn-child-poverty-eastern-europe>

maintain financial stability². In addition, sanctions imposed on Russia disrupted supply chains and restricted access to critical resources, further exacerbating economic imbalances in the region.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The geopolitical and socio-economic consequences of the Russian-Ukrainian war have become one of the key topics of modern scientific research, attracting the attention of researchers in the field of international relations, economics and security. Modern scientific discussion characterizes the impact of the war on regional stability, energy security, economic development of Eastern European countries and global economic processes³.

Al-Saidi⁴ examines the role of the Middle East in ensuring Europe's energy security against the backdrop of reduced supplies from Russia, emphasizing the importance of diversifying energy resources. Research indicates the complex nature of the consequences of the war, covering both social and economic aspects of life in the countries of the region.

Žuk⁵ examines the impact of war on the European labor market, noting the deterioration of employment conditions, especially among low-skilled workers and migrants. Hryhorczuk et al.⁶ examine the environmental consequences of war, pointing to environmental pollution due to the destruction of infrastructure and the use of heavy

² B. M. Jenkins, *Consequences of the war in Ukraine: The economic fallout*, (RAND Corporation, 2023). <https://www.rand.org/pubs/commentary/2023/03/consequences-of-the-war-in-ukraine-the-economic-fallout.html>

³ P. K. Ozili, "Global economic consequence of Russian invasion of Ukraine," *SSRN Electronic Journal*, (2022). <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4064770>; O. Petryk, "Consequences of the war for the global economy and some European countries: Czechia", *VoXUkraine*, (2022). <https://voxukraine.org/en/consequences-of-the-war-for-the-global-economy-and-some-european-countries-czechia>; A. Prohorovs, "Russia's war in Ukraine: Consequences for European countries' businesses and economies," *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, Vol. 15, No. 7 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm15070295>; S. Rostetska et al., "Formation of a new paradigm of global political and migration processes under the influence of military activities in Ukraine," *Baltic Journal of Economic Studies*, Vol. 9, No. 5 (2023), p. 241–251. <https://doi.org/10.30525/2256-0742/2023-9-5-241-251>; A. Soliman, E. Le Saout, "The impact of the war in Ukraine on the idiosyncratic risk and the market risk," *Finance Research Letters*, Vol. 60 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.frl.2023.104895>

⁴ M. Al-Saidi, "White knight or partner of choice? The Ukraine war and the role of the Middle East in the energy security of Europe," *Energy Strategy Reviews*, Vol. 49 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2023.101116>

⁵ P. Žuk, "The war in Ukraine: Consequences for the economy, labor class and equitable development in Europe and beyond," *Economic and Labor Relations Review*, Vol. 34, No. 2 (2023), p. 343–356. <https://doi.org/10.1017/elr.2023.18>

⁶ D. Hryhorczuk et al., "The environmental health impacts of Russia's war on Ukraine," *Journal of Occupational Medicine and Toxicology*, Vol. 19 (2024, December 1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12995-023-00398-y>

weapons. Cafruny et al.⁷ analyze the crisis of global strategies in the context of war, emphasizing the changing approaches to security policy in Europe.

Gong⁸ focuses on the economic consequences of the war for EU countries, noting the reduction in trade volumes, the increase in energy costs, and the decline in the region's investment attractiveness. Ennen and Wozny⁹ analyze the transport consequences of the conflict, the closure of airspace, which led to an increase in the cost of air tickets between Europe and Asia. Shahi¹⁰ offers a geopolitical analysis of the war, emphasizing the strategic importance of Ukraine for the security architecture of Europe and the world. These studies demonstrate the need to develop comprehensive approaches to crisis management and strengthen regional security.

The works studied cover issues of economic security, migration challenges, energy dependence, and regional policy transformation. In general, scholars agree on the significant impact of the war on the socio-economic stability of Eastern Europe, emphasizing the importance of strengthening cooperation between countries and adapting to new geopolitical realities.

The aim of the study was to determine the geopolitical and socio-economic consequences of the Russian-Ukrainian war for the countries of Eastern Europe in the period 2022–2024, to analyze their impact on economic stability, social security and strategic development of the region. The objectives of the study included assessing the level of economic losses, increasing social tension and transformation of energy and trade policy in war conditions, studying the processes of reorientation of trade routes and reducing dependence on Russian energy carriers. The practical significance of the work lies in formulating recommendations for the countries of Eastern Europe on strengthening regional security, effective adaptation to geopolitical challenges, and developing strategies for sustainable economic development in conditions of protracted geopolitical instability.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research procedure consisted of several consecutive stages aimed at a comprehensive analysis of the geopolitical and socio-economic consequences of the

⁷ A. Cafruny et al. "Ukraine, multipolarity and the crisis of grand strategies," *Journal of Balkan and Near Eastern Studies*, Vol. 25, No. 1 (2023), p. 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19448953.2022.2084881>

⁸ Y. Gong, "Economic consequences in Europe of the Russian-Ukraine 2022 war," *Advances in Economics, Management and Political Sciences*, Vol. 4, No. 1 (2023), p. 260–270. <https://doi.org/10.54254/2754-1169/4/20221073>

⁹ D. Ennen, F. Wozny, "Airspace closures following the war of aggression in Ukraine: The impact on Europe-Asia airfares," *Transportation Research Proceedings*, 78 (2024), p. 103–110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2024.02.014>

¹⁰ D. K. Shahi, "War in Ukraine: A geopolitical analysis," *International Journal of Research in Social Science*, Vol. 12 (2022), 2249–2496. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/361098792_War_in_Ukraine_A_Geopolitical_Analysis

Russian-Ukrainian war for the countries of Eastern Europe. The first stage was to determine the theoretical basis of the study, which included the collection and study of relevant analytical documents, strategic plans of the European Union, reports of international organizations and expert assessments. Particular attention was paid to official publications of such organizations as the European Council, the European Investment Bank, UNICEF, RAND Corporation and others. The next stage was the systematization of the collected information and the identification of key indicators for further analysis of economic, social and geopolitical aspects. After that, quantitative and qualitative data analysis was carried out, which allowed to identify the main trends, relationships and patterns. The final stage was the generalization of the research results, the preparation of tables, visualizations and the formulation of conclusions reflecting the essence of the phenomenon under study in the context of a specific topic.

The study sample covered eight Eastern European countries: Ukraine, Poland, Romania, Moldova, Lithuania, Latvia, Estonia, and Hungary. The choice of these countries is due to their geographical location, political and economic ties with Ukraine, and varying degrees of impact of the war on their internal processes. Ukraine was selected as the immediate epicenter of the conflict, while Poland, Romania, Moldova, and the Baltic countries were selected as the closest neighbors that felt the significant impact of the war through migration processes, economic shocks, and geopolitical changes. The study period covers 2022–2024, which is explained by the beginning of Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine in February 2022 and the need to track the dynamics of changes during the first three years of the conflict. The selected time period made it possible to identify not only some of the short term effects of the war but also some medium term trends in the socio-economic and political dimensions thereby assuring broadness and objectivity of the results secured. To achieve the objectives set forth, the study applied both quantitative and qualitative methods of analysis. Quantitative analysis consisted principally in the secondary analysis of statistical data obtained from open sources, official reports, and international databases.

2: ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL IMPLICATIONS OF RUSSIAN-UKRAINIAN WAR FOR EASTERN EUROPE

The Russian-Ukrainian war caused a large-scale economic shock to the countries of Eastern Europe, causing significant losses to national economies. The war destroyed production chains, caused a drop in GDP and increased inflation in the countries of the region. Poland, the Czech Republic, Romania and Hungary, which had stable economic growth in previous years, faced a significant slowdown in economic activity. In addition to the direct effects of hostilities, the war provoked an increase in unemployment, inflation and aggravation of social protection problems of the population (see Figure 1).

The wars have caused significant trade imbalances. Exports from Ukraine, which were an important source of raw materials and agricultural products for many European countries, have suffered a serious decline. The blockade of ports and the destruction of transport infrastructure have significantly complicated export deliveries, which has affected the economies of neighboring countries, especially Poland, Lithuania and

Romania, which have traditionally acted as transit hubs¹¹. Figure 2 shows the above and the imbalances in exports and imports.

Figure 1. Economic consequences of the war for Eastern European countries

Source: Compiled from European Investment Bank¹², Jenkins¹³, Redeker¹⁴, Emerson et al.¹⁵

¹¹ B. Javorcik, G. B. Wolff, *War in Ukraine: What is the effect on Central and Eastern Europe?* (Javorcik & Wolff, 2022). <https://www.Javorcik & Wolff.org/podcast/war-ukraine-what-effect-central-and-eastern-europe>

¹² *How bad is the Ukrainian war for the European recovery?* EIB Reports, (European Investment Bank, 2023). <https://www.eib.org/en/publications/how-bad-is-the-ukraine-war-for-the-european-recovery>

¹³ B. M. Jenkins, *Consequences of the war in Ukraine: The economic fallout*, (RAND Corporation, 2023). <https://www.rand.org/pubs/commentary/2023/03/consequences-of-the-war-in-ukraine-the-economic-fallout.html>

¹⁴ N. Redeker, "Same shock, different effects: EU member states' exposure to the economic consequences of Putin's war," *Jacques Delors Centre*, (2023). <https://www.delorscentre.eu/en/publications/economic-consequences-ukraine>

¹⁵ M. Emerson et al., *Russia's invasion of Ukraine and its impacts on Eastern Europe*, (CEPS, 2023). <https://www.ceps.eu/ceps-publications/russias-invasion-of-ukraine-and-its-impacts-on-eastern-europe/>

Figure 2. Changes in trade routes and export/import volumes
 Source: compiled based on Mackowiak¹⁶, European Council¹⁷

The Russian-Ukrainian war has caused an unprecedented humanitarian crisis that has significantly affected the social stability of Eastern European countries. One of the most important aspects of this crisis is the massive displacement of people. As of the end of 2023, more than 7.5 million Ukrainians had been forced to leave their homes, seeking refuge mainly in Poland, Romania, Moldova and Lithuania¹⁸. The migration flow has led to an unprecedented strain on the social systems of the host countries. For example, Poland has received about 2.3 million refugees, which is a significant share of its population. These consequences are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Social consequences of war for the population

Country	Poverty rate growth (%)	Number of refugees (million people)	Reduction in access to health services (%)
Ukraine	30	7.5	40
Poland	8	2.3	15
Romania	10	1.1	18
Moldova	20	0.7	25

¹⁶ M. Mackowiak, *War's impact on Eastern European trade routes — Perspective from Poland*, (FourKites, 2023). <https://www.fourkites.com/blogs/wars-impact-on-eastern-european-trade-routes-perspective-from-poland/>

¹⁷ *Energy prices and security of supply*, (Council of the European Union, 2024). <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/energy-prices-and-security-of-supply/#EU>

¹⁸ *The impact of the war in Ukraine and subsequent economic downturn on child poverty in Eastern Europe*, (UNICEF, 2023). <https://www.unicef.org/eca/reports/impact-war-ukraine-and-subsequent-economic-downturn-child-poverty-eastern-europe>

Country	Poverty rate growth (%)	Number of refugees (million people)	Reduction in access to health services (%)
Lithuania	12	0.5	20

Source: Compiled from UNICEF¹⁹, Emerson et al.²⁰, Redeker²¹, Niculescu²²

A critical aspect of the social consequences of war is the reduction in access to health services. This is most felt by residents of Ukraine, where about 40% of the population faced restrictions on access to medical facilities due to destroyed infrastructure and hospitals being overwhelmed by the wounded and refugees. In Poland and Romania, the figure rose to 15-18% since health systems were overwhelmed by additional patients. In the case of Moldova and Lithuania, access to health services was reduced by about 20-25% due to both the influx of refugees and the lack of funding. The situation becomes more complicated because a significant part of the medical staff has either fled Ukraine or has been mobilized; this has led to the lack of qualified personnel in this region. Table 2 presents the aforementioned changes in energy policy and social challenges, as well as the overall geopolitical consequences of the Russian-Ukrainian war for the countries of Eastern Europe, which are discussed in more detail below.

3: GEOPOLITICAL CONSEQUENCES FOR EASTERN EUROPE COUNTRIES

Table 2. Geopolitical consequences of the Russian-Ukrainian war for the countries of Eastern Europe

Category	Specific consequences	Short description
Security and	Expanding NATO's presence	Increasing Alliance bases in

¹⁹ *The impact of the war in Ukraine and subsequent economic downturn on child poverty in Eastern Europe*, (UNICEF, 2023). <https://www.unicef.org/eca/reports/impact-war-ukraine-and-subsequent-economic-downturn-child-poverty-eastern-europe>

²⁰ M. Emerson et al., *Russia's invasion of Ukraine and its impacts on Eastern Europe*, (CEPS, 2023). <https://www.ceps.eu/ceps-publications/russias-invasion-of-ukraine-and-its-impacts-on-eastern-europe/>

²¹ N. Redeker, "Same shock, different effects: EU member states' exposure to the economic consequences of Putin's war," *Jacques Delors Centre*, (2023). <https://www.delorscentre.eu/en/publications/economic-consequences-ukraine>

²² L. Niculescu, *Russia's war in Eastern Europe is a central threat to the international architecture*, (Robert Niculescu L. Foundation, 2022). <https://www.robert-niculescu.eu/en/european-interviews/115-russia-s-war-in-eastern-europe-is-a-central-threat-to-the-international-architecture>

military cooperation		Poland, Romania and the Baltic countries.
	Rising defense spending	Countries in the region have raised military budgets above 2% of GDP.
	Deepening alliances	More active cooperation with the USA, France and Britain.
Energy independence	Reduction of gas imports from Russia	Eastern Europe reduced purchases by more than 50%.
	LNG infrastructure development	Poland and Lithuania have opened new gas terminals.
	Growth of renewable energy	Increased investment in solar and wind energy.
Political stability and EU integration	Ukraine is a candidate for the EU	Granting the status strengthened European unity.
	Reforms in Moldova and Georgia	Supporting European integration changes in the region.
	Development of regional cooperation	Activation of the "Three Seas" and "Visegrad Four" initiatives.
Trade and logistics	Reduction in imports from the Russian Federation	Eastern Europe has reduced purchases of oil and metals.
	Ukraine's exports to the EU	Growth in agricultural product supplies through Poland and Romania.
	Turkey's role in transit	Turkish ports have become key to regional logistics.
Migration and social challenges	The influx of Ukrainian refugees	About 7 million people arrived in neighboring countries.
	Demographic changes	Refugees have impacted the labor market and education.
	Growing social burden	Countries' budgets have allocated more funds for aid.

Source: developed by the authors

The war forced the European Union to reconsider its foreign policy priorities. One of the main decisions was to grant Ukraine the status of candidate country for EU membership, which demonstrated European solidarity and support for democratic

transformations²³. In parallel, the EU intensified cooperation with the Eastern Partnership countries, Moldova and Georgia, which are striving for European integration.

DISCUSSION

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4-1: SUSTAINABILITY CONCERNS AND GEOPOLITICAL DYNAMICS CHANGES

The results of this study on the geopolitical consequences of the Russian-Ukrainian war for Eastern European countries confirm and complement the findings presented in the contemporary literature. Da Costa et al.²⁴ emphasize that the war significantly increased threats to sustainable development, especially in the context of post-pandemic recovery. Such conclusions are also consistent with our results, which showed that Eastern European countries face double pressures due to military actions and the lingering effects of the COVID-19 pandemic. Similarly, Zavadzka²⁵ emphasizes that the conflict significantly changed the geopolitical dynamics of Central and Eastern Europe, exacerbating regional contradictions and intensifying the search for new alliances, which was reflected in our study in the issue of strengthening NATO's eastern flank.

4-2: SOCIETAL PRESSURES

The social consequences of war, especially in the context of migration and demographic change, have been widely covered both in our study and in the reviewed publications. Opiola et al.²⁶ examine the refugee crisis on the eastern border of the EU, demonstrating significant pressure on social services in host countries, an observation that is consistent with our analysis of increased health and social welfare spending in

²³ M. Emerson et al., *Russia's invasion of Ukraine and its impacts on Eastern Europe*, (CEPS, 2023) <https://www.ceps.eu/ceps-publications/russias-invasion-of-ukraine-and-its-impacts-on-eastern-europe/>

²⁴ J. P. da Costa et al., "Threats to sustainability in the face of post-pandemic scenarios and the war in Ukraine," *Science of The Total Environment*, Vol. 892 (2023, September 20), p. 164509. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.164509>

²⁵ O. Zavadzka, "The borders of the 'near abroad': The Russian war in Ukraine and its consequences for the geopolitical system of Central and Eastern Europe," *Studia Historica Gedanensia*, Vol. 13 (2022), p. 278–293. <https://doi.org/10.4467/23916001hg.22.018.17438>

²⁶ W. Opiola et al., "War and politics: The 2022 Russian invasion of Ukraine and refugee crisis on the eastern EU border from the perspective of border studies," *Pogranicze. Polish Borderlands Studies*, Vol. 10, No. 1 (2022), p. 7-22. <https://doi.org/10.25167/brs4791>

Poland and Romania. Newton et al.²⁷ draw attention to the increased risk of typhus due to mass population movements, which coincides with the problems of reduced access to health services identified in our study. Kratochvíl and O'Sullivan²⁸ add to this context by examining the gender dimension of the conflict, highlighting the increase in gender inequality and social vulnerability, aspects that were taken into account when assessing socio-economic changes in the region.

4-3: ENVIRONMENTAL BURDEN AGGRAVATION

Environmental impacts, although less widely discussed, are critical to understanding the long-term impacts of conflict. Da Costa et al.²⁹ highlight the increasing levels of environmental pollution resulting from military action and the destruction of infrastructure. Accordingly, this was also confirmed in our study, which recorded an increase in the environmental burden on border regions, associated with an increase in industrial activity to provide new logistics routes. Thus, the results of the study are corroborated by a wide array of modern scientific sources, focusing on the ways in which the Russian-Ukrainian war impacts Eastern European countries in a number of dimensions.

CONCLUSION

5:

A wide-ranging analysis of geopolitical and socio-economic consequences of the Russian-Ukrainian war for the countries of Eastern Europe within the timespan 2022-2024 was conducted by the study. The study results showed that war became an agent of radical change in this region and had had its negative impact on economic stability, social security, and geopolitical balance. Most severe impacts have included sharp GDP reductions, growing inflation, increased unemployment and poverty, especially in Ukraine and countries adjoining the war zone. A massive movement of refugees displaced millions and caused a migration crisis. This has burdened Poland, Romania, Moldova, and the Baltic countries with increased demographic change and impact on labor markets. In terms of security, the war's geopolitical dimension was manifested in enhanced cooperation on security within NATO, a reorientation of the energy policies

²⁷ P. N. Newton et al., "Fournier, PE, Tappe, D., & Richards, AL (2022). Renewed risk for epidemic typhus related to war and massive population displacement, Ukraine," *Emerging Infectious Diseases*, Vol. 28, No. 10 (2022), p. 2125–2126. <https://doi.org/10.3201/eid2810.220776>

²⁸ P. Kratochvíl, M. O'Sullivan, "A war like no other: Russia's invasion of Ukraine as a war on gender order," *European Security*, Vol. 32, No. 3 (2023), p. 347–366. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09662839.2023.2236951>

²⁹ J. P. da Costa et al., "Threats to sustainability in the face of post-pandemic scenarios and the war in Ukraine," *Science of The Total Environment*, Vol. 892 (2023, September 20), p. 164509. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.164509>

of the countries of the region, and a degree acceleration of processes of European integration for Ukraine and other Eastern Partnership countries. However, the EU's sanctions policy towards Russia has acquired a new distribution of trade flows and deepened the energy crisis, affecting both industrial and household activities in the EU member states.

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